

Implicature found in Balinese Selebgram Contents on Instagram

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Abstract

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Instagram is a popular social networking site for people of all ages. Instagram has lately been used by peoples to conduct online business. They are known as *Selebgram* or *Instagram Celebrities*, they are usually using this platform to promote goods, foods, beverages or services on Instagram. Celebrities or influencers with a large number of followers are typically quite creative when it comes to developing content. This study focuses on the usage of language in posting video content to the accounts *@gek indah25* and *@alitwerdisuputra*. The role or use of language by a person referred to as a celebrity becomes significant. The commercial language is not usually expressed clearly, as is the actual meaning. The context and situation must come before the usage of languages. The objective of this research is to determine the types of implicature on the Instagram endorsement video by Balinese *Selebgram*. In the research, two forms of implicatures were discovered: conventional implicature and conversational implicature. The qualitative method was applied in this study.

1. Introduction

In this modern era, technological developments affected all human activities. Various kinds of new and updated technologies become a guide for humans in carrying out their daily lives. An example of technology that is developing rapidly today is the media. Along with the COVID-19 pandemic, which provides media opportunities, especially online media, to develop even more. It is

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undeniable that this is one of the reasons that make online media with various facilities or features increasingly diverse. It can be said that the role of the media, especially during the Covid-19 outbreak, is very important, the media plays a role in all matters relating to information during the Covid-19 outbreak. Media helps humans as social beings to interact and communicate. Communication is an important thing in human social life (Rahmayani et al., 2022; Hombing & Sipahutar, 2022; Siregar & Wolor, 2023). Communication is a process by which an idea possessed by a person is then transferred to one or more recipients to change their behavior. Process communication must be supported by several elements such as the sender (source), message (message), channel/media (channel), receiver (receiver) and affect/effect (Rogers in Cangara, 2015: 22).

Based on the situation and conditions during a pandemic which does not provide space for humans to socialize or interact directly, it impacted in various ways. One of the impacts is in the economic field. The development of media; whose purpose is to provide information and entertainment also expanded into the economic realm, thus providing opportunities for anyone to develop. Therefore, many people are tried their luck to be prominent and have many followers on social media accounts. The number of social media certainly gives opportunities to new people who become celebrities in the media. Someone who famous on Instagram is usually referred to as a *selebgram*. When social media becomes an influential thing in human life, there will also so many who will use social media as a place to compete for opportunities both economically and for fame.

Promoting something, such as an online business is not always easy, something useful and needed exists. It also needs creativity in using social media (Gray & Fox, 2018). When online transactions are done online, many entrepreneurs use a strategy as an attraction to offer goods or services. Being an Instagram Celebrities has become a trend among the people in Indonesia, as well as the people in Bali. *Selebgram* is an abbreviation of Instagram Celebrities or it also can be said as an influencer. In matter of fact, *Selebgram* has become famous on social media, especially Instagram. *Selebgrams* are the same as celebrities in general. The difference is that they become well-known celebrities through social media, not by the TV screen. It is said to be a *selebgram* because it has thousands, one hundred thousand or even more than a million of followers. The state of the *selebgram* begins with the uniqueness and characteristics of the content created. Millions of followers make *selebgram* targeted by entrepreneurs, governments and others people to be able to help them to promote something. The term commonly used is endorsed. The number of followers will be directly proportional to the impact and price of each endorsement that a celebrity gets.

Celebrities who are said to be influencers must have the power to influence many people, especially their followers. The positive and negative impacts always coincide with the emergence of this celebrity phenomenon. Many things could be imitated by our society from a *selebgram*, such as how to dress, routines, and the order of language used. In this regard, the use of language by the *selebgrams*, as a characteristic that they have, can attract the audience. Language is indeed important in social life, although in the past two years, many things have been restricted, including direct communication. Although the role or the use of the language that used by a person called a celebrity becomes important. The language of trade is not always said clearly, like the literal meaning. The use of languages must be followed by the context and situation. In this regard, this study will discuss the use of any types of implicature found in endorsement posts by Balinese celebrities such as @gek_indah25 and @alitwerdisuputra.

Many studies related to the types of implicatures have been conducted, for example, research from Hikmah & Irma (2021). This study described the conventional implicature analysis contained in memes in the newspaper Radar Tegal. The conventional implicature was more to provide explanations or information, educate and influence news related to demonstrations, human

trafficking and terrorist events. The similarity of this research is that both of the studies are implicatures studies. However, both of them come with different objects of study. Similarly, the research methods both use qualitative methods.

Furthermore, there is a research study related to the conversational implicatures of the Balinese *selebgram*. This study stated that the posts of Balinese celebrities, especially on the Instagram account *@gek_Cantik25*, contain a lot of conversational implicatures related to assertive, declarative and expressive speech acts (Warmadewi, 2021). The research is the same as this study. The data were taken from Instagram. The research focuses on only one celebrity, but in this study, research data were taken from two Balinese *selebgram*.

The research that was conducted by Sari, et al in 2020, is related to the analysis of implicature meaning. The study analyzes the meaning in the discourse of public service advertisements that take data from social media. The study taken was a discourse but discusses the existence of implicatures. The results of the study found that there are 3 (three) meanings in the discourse, such as giving an appeal or invitation, prohibition or innuendo, and warning.

Some of the studies mentioned above are related to this research. In its development, current research uses social media as a source of research data. As technology develops, research also develops, as well as research data. Celebrity as one of the existing phenomena, especially in Bali has its characteristics. The characteristic in question is the use of Balinese as the language of instruction in the endorsement videos that already uploaded by the Balinese *Selebgrams*.

The use of language that is related to context and situation cannot be separated from pragmatic studies. Pragmatics is a branch of linguistics that study how linguistic units are applied in communication, pragmatics is the study of language structures externally (Wijana and Rohmadi, 2009). Along with the times, many current studies use pragmatics as one of the theories used. The number of social media that increase means the more that can be analyzed from the pragmatic side. This is related to digital developments, pragmatics also indirectly synergizes, growing side by side with information technology and digital technology, which can be called Cyberpragmatics (Rahardi, 2020).

Implicature is one of the studies in the field of pragmatics. The concept of implicature conveyed Grice said that implicature is speech that has a hidden meaning conveyed by the speaker or addresses. In this case, the concept of implicature is often said to be a differentiator regarding "what is said," with "what is implied" (Leech, 1983). Implicature is an expression whose meaning is not directly reflected in the vocabulary expressed (Ihsan, 2011: 93). According to Levinson, implicature has several concepts, such as; (a) implicature can provide a meaningful functional explanation of unexplained linguistic facts, which are then put into the exception bins by formal grammatical theories; (b) implicature can provide an explanation why an utterance, for example in the form of a question but means a command, (c) implicature can simplify the semantic description of differences between clauses, and implicature can explain various linguistic phenomena that seem unrelated or even contradictory but turns out to have a communicative relationship (Levinson, 1992, 97-100).

Grice (in Leech, 1983: 17) distinguishes implicature into two, namely conventional implicature and conversational implicature. Conventional implicature is a pragmatic implication that is obtained directly from the meaning of the word, not from the principles of conversation. Meanwhile, conversational implicatures have more varied meanings and meanings. The meaning of the utterance is very dependent on the context in which the conversation occurs. Conversational implicature is an implicature that occurs when "what is implied" is different from "what is said".

2. Materials and Methods

Social media as a data source made researchers directly involved in observing and collecting data in the form of Balinese speech from celebrities on Instagram. Researchers did not only observe and record the data that were needed in this study. In this case, the researcher was one of the research instruments where the researcher is a data collection tool (Moleong, 2006). The data collection method used in this study was the listening and writing method by listening to Balinese speech used by Balinese celebrities. The use of the listening method was realized through basic techniques and advanced techniques. The basic technique uses tapping techniques, then proceeds with free listening and speaking techniques and note-taking techniques (Sudaryanto, 2015). In addition, the documentation method was also one of the methods used in this study to make it easier to transcribe data in the form of videos.

Qualitative research that emphasizes meaning, focuses more on quality data with qualitative analysis (Sutopo, 2006: 48). This research was related to previous research. While the previous study on Balinese Language Politeness by Bali *Selebgram* on Instagram social media reviewed language politeness, the current research focuses on the implicatures of endorsement content. This research was also conducted to find out the existence of the Balinese language on social media, especially on Instagram. Thus, the Balinese language as one of the elements of Balinese culture can be maintained.

3. Results and Discussions

Conventional Implicature

1. Context: A boyfriend asks where they are going.

Cowok : kamu dot makan ape ?

Cewek : ter..(dihentikan si cowok)

Cowok : pasti kel nyawab terserah jeleme ne, mending langsung gen ajak ke tempat tujuan (ucapnya dalam hati)

Cowok : eeee.. ke kopi ridho yuk yank?

Cewek : kopi ridho?

Cowok : ae, ditu ade tongkrongan baru selain menu ne to ade kopi lumpur, es teh lumpur, godoh gula bali, makanan, pokokne megenep ade ditu yank

The conversations that occur above are conventional implicature which do not have hidden meanings. This can be identified from "*eeee .. ke kopi ridho yuk yang?*". The purpose of the speech is to invite his girlfriend to a place called Kopi Ridho to eat

2. Context: Gek Cantik is reprimanding a small child who rides an electric bicycle on the street without proper equipment.

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Gek cantik : *wih putu,,nak ngudiang cenik-cenik ngabe motor masuk ? bahaya tawang.. helm sing nganggo, SIM sing ngelah, misi ngajak adik pere. Sing nawang bahaya..*

Anak-anak : *ape montor, yee nak sepeda.. hahahaha ketinggalan hahaha*

The conversation above is in the conventional implicature, which means the speech of the Gek Cantik character regarding the use of helmets and other equipment on the road is a must and common knowledge that is known by many people. This is evidenced by the utterance "...*helm sing nganggo, SIM sing ngelah, misi ngajak adik pere. Sing nawang bahaya.*". The purpose of the speech is to remind people when driving to obey the rules and use the appropriate equipment.

3. Context: Gek Cantik meets someone who brings her dream vehicle.

Gek cantik : *Miih luung sajan bli, lamun keto baang tyang nyilih cepok bli nah ?*

Bli alit : *Yihh..adi nyilih bli kel kundangan jani*

Gek cantik : *Mih jeg tenget san.. pasti di Jakarta meli bli ae ?*

Bli alit : *Hahaha ngudiang di Jakarta, Sentrik to nak sube ada di Denpasar alamatne di Jl, Gatot Subroto Barat No. 500 Denpasar , gek. Sentrik ento merupakan distributor kendaraan listrik terbesar di Bali bahkan di Indonesia. Lamun meli kendaraan listrik harus di Sentrik gek.*

The data above is taken from a conversation between Bli Alit and Gek Cantik in a video endorsement of an electric bicycle product. The utterance is classified as conventional implicature on "...*alamatne di Jl, Gatot Subroto Barat No. 500 Denpasar , gek. ...*". The purpose of the speech is to show the address of a shop that the two characters will go to.

Conversation Implicature

1. Context: The character Wi saw Gek Cantik playing social media, while today is *Rahinan* (holy) day.

Wi : *"hei..kamu nawang rahinan jani?"*

Gek cantik : *"sing nawang"*

Wi : *"jani saraswati "*

Gek cantik : *"pkokne ape orang wi, tyang sing nyak ke pura jani"*

Wi : *"Adi keto"*

Gek cantik : *"Kebaya sing ngelah wi "*

In the conversation that occurs between the two characters above, there are conversational implicatures in the "*jani saraswati*" speech. Wi's intention was not only to tell Gek Cantik about the *rahinan* day, but also to tell her to stop playing on social media and go to the temple to pray. Without

seeing and knowing the whole conversation, the true meaning of Wi's character will not be known, therefore this fragment of conversation contains conversational implications.

2. Context: Character Wi wants Gek Cantik to go to the temple, but Gek Cantik refuses.

Gek cantik : "Ae be tawang tyang wi, tapi kan rahinan di bali nak liu. Ade galungan, ade kuningan, ade sugian bali, sugian jawa, purnama, tilem, kajeng kliwon. Jani ne kel teka saraswati, wi. Kebaya tyang sing ngelah tawang, telah sube stok kebaya e. Masak kebaya to to gen anggo? Kan lek ati ajak timpal-timpal ajak pisaga"

Wi : "Ee gek, gek kal ke pura ape kal fashion show? Nawang tujuan ke pura ento? Nak kel ngaturang bhakti menghadap Ida Sang hyang Widhi Wasa , gek "

Gek cantik : " Be je keto wi, tapi kan lek ati ajak pisaga ajak timpal-timpale. Masa kebaya to to gen anggo tawang"

Wi : "Lanjutang, lanjutang, wi kal berangkat malu nah.."

Gek cantik : "Aden me-tiktok an..ganggu san"

In the data above, the conversational implicature is detected, because there is an utterance that implies something different from what is said. This is evident in the snippet of "*Lanjutang, lanjutang, wi kal berangkat malu nah...*" When viewed from the whole conversation, the sentence implies that actually Wi hopes Gek Cantik will go to the temple with him, but Gek Cantik prefers to play social media.

3. Context: Couple was meeting.

Cewe (jadi cowo): Cang pesu malu nah

Cowok (jadi cewek) : Hey..jangan tinggalin aku

Cowok (jadi cewek) : Aduh yang seduk ajan, beli maem yuk

The conversational implicature can be seen in the sentence "Ouch, it's okay, let's buy some maem" in the conversational fragment above. The character's story revolves around his desire to accompany his girlfriend because he knows her boyfriend is going out. Because the actual meanings of the words that make up the utterances differ greatly, this data belongs to conversational implicatures, which require context to determine the true meaning. Context: Gek Cantik just got back from the market.

Gek cantik : haduh kenyel san tyang bli, dibi baange gae biin tyang peteng ajak kurenane ube keto semengane biin tyang bangun kal rahinan, kene be bek san tyang ngabe blanjaan bli. Bli kal kije to ? wih ape tegakin bli ne? Jeg busan liu san masih tepuk tyang e negakin sepeda ape motor.. pokokne kene be tepuk tyang bli.

Bli alit : ooh ne madan sepeda listrik gek, salah satu produk ne sentrik

Gek cantik : hah? Sepeda listrik? Men ape bedane ajak motor bli?

Bli alit : Ini kendaraan ramah lingkungan gek, selain untuk bisa berolahraga yen kenyel nguyeng pedal tinggal gas..eee..eee..ooo

Gek cantik : Emangne sing mliang bensin bli ?

Bli alit : Adane gen sube sepeda listrik, ya jelaslah maman ne listrik

In the data above, the data included in the conversational implicature is on the utterance "*ooh ne madan sepeda listrik gek, salah satu produk ne sentrik*". The utterances not only provide information about what object is being used but also inform the place that sells these objects. The purpose of the above speech is to promote a place that sells electric bicycles.

4. Conclusion

The data in the following study was obtained from the videos made by the owner of the @GekCantik, in partnership with another influencer named @alitwerdisuputra. Implicatures in language are an intriguing topic to study since they are frequently employed in everyday life and require the capacity to comprehend what they represent. According to the findings of the data analysis, there are two types of implicatures: traditional implicature and conversational implicature. The distinctions between the two are dependent on how the context of the data might convey the meaning of the utterances.

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References

- Cangara, H. (2015). *Pengantar Ilmu Komunikasi* (Edisi Kedu). PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Gray, N. &, & Fox, M. (2018). *Social Media Marketing* (2nd ed.).
- Hikmah, E. N., & Irma, C. N. (2021). Analisis Implikatur Konvensional Meme dalam Surat Kabar Radar Tegal. *Jurnal Literasi*, 5(1).
- Hombing, H. B., & Sipahutar, C. A. (2022). Implementation of 'ruth and naomi' interpersonal communication as a model in avoiding toxic relationship. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 4(1), 424-431.
- Ihsan, D. (2011). *Pragmatik, Analisis Wacana, dan Guru Bahasa*. Universitas Sriwijaya.
- Leech, G. N. (1983). *Principles of Pragmatics*. Longman.
- Levinson, S. (1992). *Pragmatic*. Cambridge University Press.
- Moleong, L. J. (2006). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Rahardi, R. K. (2020). *Pragmatik Konteks Ekstralinguistik dalam Perspektif Cyberpragmatics*. Amara Books.
- Rahmayani, A., Nurhaeni, I. D. A., & Satyawan, I. A. (2022). Family communication of health workers during the covid-19 pandemic: A review of interaction adaptation. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 4(2), 45-53.
- Siregar, A., & Wolor, C. W. (2023). Communication and work environment on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 5(1), 184-194.
- Sudaryanto. (2015). *Metode dan aneka teknik analisis bahasa*. Sanata Dharma University Press.
- Sutopo. (2006). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. UNS PRESS.
- Warmadewi, A. (2021). Implikatur dalam Percakapan Selebgram Bali Gek_Cantik25. *Linguistik Jurnal Bahasa Dan Sastra*, 6(1).
- Wijana and Rohmadi. (2009). *Analisis Wacana Praktis : Kajian Teor dan Analisis*. Yuma Pustaka.